

ASSESSMENT OF NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF PRE & POST-OPERATIVE CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING (CABG) SURGERY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Objective: To assess nutritional status of pre-operative and post-operative Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting (CABG) patients and to find out relationship between nutrition and rehabilitation after cardiac surgery.

Background: Coronary artery bypass grafting improves coronary blood flow to the heart in severe coronary artery disease. In cardiac surgery patient's malnutrition is aggravated by long time pre-operative fasting and delay of nutrition support post-operatively. Nutrition support improves the recovery of patients in many ways.

Methods: Study was conducted at Rawalpindi Institute of Cardiology. Anthropomorphic, biochemical and clinical, data collected through semi quantitative questionnaire from February 2025 to April 2025 from 65 patients who were admitted at intensive care unit and cardiac surgery ward for coronary artery bypass grafting surgery. Serum albumin levels, hemoglobin levels were measured and dietary data was collected through food frequency questionnaire and 24 hour recall. Data analyzed through SPSS software and Nutri-survey software.

Results: 36(55.3%) subjects were overweight, 7(10.7%) subjects were obese. 51(76.1%) were doing daily walk. 61% subjects were smoking, 55% had hypertension, 30.70% subjects were suffering from diabetes mellitus type I and type II. 30.7% had Hypernatremia. 58.40% were suffering from pre-operative hypoalbuminemia, 67.60% found post hypoalbuminemia, 40% pre-operative patients had chest pain, 22% had fatigue and 22% had arrhythmia. Strong relationship found between low levels of serum albumin levels and prolongs stay in hospital. BMI >25 overweight and prolong stay in hospital found strong relationship. Poor nutritional status also causing delay healing in wound, prolong hospitalization, complications and readmission.

Conclusion: Poor nutritional status, hypoalbuminemia and BMI >25 found

delay in wound healing, prolong hospitalization, other complications. Post-operative patients had more poor nutritional status than preoperative patients

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) improves blood flow to the heart in severe coronary artery disease (CAD). Coronary arteries supply oxygen to the heart, and CAD is a condition of the heart in which a plaque of fat, cholesterol, calcium and any other substance which is present in the blood develop inside the arteries, which can cause blockage and reduce blood flow to the heart, and cause heart attack (Alexander & Smith, 2016).

CAD is one of the most common cause of death internationally, even with advance technology, advance medicines and ways of treatment have been discovered but developed countries also face the problem with developing countries, and it is predicted that CAD will be most frequent reason of death for the next 20 years. CABG is that procedure which reduce morbidity and mortality at some extent (Burkauskas et al., 2018). CAD related with smoking, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, abdominal obesity, regular alcohol consumption and low physical activity cause myocardial infarction. In Pakistan coronary artery disease is the 2nd leading cause of death and contributes to 13% of all deaths. Coronary artery bypass grafting was introduced in 1968 and had better quality of life and good survival as compared to medical therapy. A number of factors increase the risk of developing the heart disease. Reducing or eliminating these risk factors can be helpful, even if a person already has heart disease or has had a heart attack in past. Cardiac bypass surgery aims to reduce the risk factors for heart disease and includes strategies to help patients and family members to stop smoking, control high blood pressure, improve cholesterol levels, begin exercising regularly, reduce weight if necessary, and reduce stress in patients. Some of these changes can be made by adjusting lifestyle habits through diet and exercise. However, lifestyle changes alone may not be adequate and medications are often needed (Bandara, Ekanayake, Kapuruge, & Wanigatunge, 2016).

Cardiac surgery can cause a further decline in nutritional status due to postoperative catabolic reaction and a decrease in dietary intake (DI).

Previous studies reported that approximately 0.90 g/dl of serum albumin was lost in the perioperative period. Although it may be due to poor nutritional status or the catabolic reactions from surgery, postoperative DI is thought to be reduced due to loss of appetite or lack of taste in food (M. Ogawa et al., 2019).

In cardiac surgery patient's malnutrition is aggravated by long time pre-operative fasting and delay of nutrition support post-operatively. Nutrition support improves the recovery of patients in many ways, such as; maintenance of metabolism and catabolism, maintenance of gut integrity, reduction of complications after surgery, enhance wound healing and secure proper hydration. Pre-operative time is very important time to optimize nutritional status, correct deficiencies, and enhance immune defense mechanism before surgery. This may lower the risk of developing complications after surgery (Hill, Nesterova, Lomivorotov, Efremov, Goetzenich, Benstoem, Zamyatin, et al., 2018).

Surgical trauma can result in immobilization of biological material, degradation of muscle proteins, synthesis of acute-phase protein synthesis liver, occurrence of catabolism phase and anabolism simultaneously and as a consequence weight loss and nutritional deficiencies. Low levels of albumin lead to edema and mucosal atrophy as well as excessive bacterial growth which, in turns disrupt absorption. Deficiency of immunoglobulin A (IgA), vitamin C, and glutamine favors the occurrence of immunological disorders. A decrease in weight of over 4.5 kg within three months increases the risk of pre-operative mortality 19 times (Ścisło et al., 2019).

Malnutrition is commonly seen in the elderly with heart failure and is associated with greater mortality; thus, it is a problem that requires a solution. Poor nutritional status can also be related to the catabolic state and muscle wasting known as "sarcopenia" and is reported to be a predictor of long-term survival after

cardiothoracic surgery. Poor preoperative nutritional status is associated with muscle wasting and is a predictor of the retardation of functional recovery after cardiac surgery (DiMaria-Ghalili, 2002).

Improper nutritional status is characterized not only by malnutrition, but also by overweight and obesity. Obesity is currently a social problem and the cause of metabolic disorders. It creates a number of problems in everyday life; difficulties with movement, constraints in private life and professional life activities, lack of acceptance by the environment (Lobstein, Neveux, Landon, & consortium, 2018).

Nutritional support is recognized as a clinically relevant aspect of the intensive care treatment of cardiac surgery patients. Patients with cardiac surgery regularly experience a systemic inflammatory response, which may contribute to persistent and acute organ injury. The nutritional status and adequate nutritional therapy are contributing to the outcome of the patients (Hill, Nesterova, Lomivorotov, Efremov, Goetzenich, Benstoem, Zamyantin, et al., 2018). Elderly people are particularly vulnerable to the occurrence of nutritional disorders. They are affected by general factors, but also age-specific, biological and psychosocial ones. The most significant are: process of aging of specific organs, loss of appetite, disturbances of taste and smell, systemic diseases, pharmacotherapy, limited activity level, material status and mental health (Sipahi, Akay, Dagdelen, Blitz, & Alhan, 2014).

Due to increases in life expectancy and the higher incidence of cardiovascular disease associated with advanced age, the number of elderly patients undergoing cardiac surgery is growing worldwide (Leung Wai Sang, Chaturvedi, Iqbal, Lachapelle, & de Varennes, 2012).

Especially in Japan as the front-runner of super-aged societies, older patients are becoming a public health problem. Almost 25 % of all patients undergoing cardiac surgery are over 70 years old. These patients frequently present with age-dependent co-morbidities and physical limitations (Masuda et al., 2018).

In the case of elderly people, eating disorders concern mainly patients with various types of disorders of respective systems. One of the most

common disorder is atherosclerosis, which is associated with the occurrence of negative cardiovascular events and often subject to surgical treatments. In patients with myocardial ischemia, percutaneous coronary interventions (PCI) or coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) are performed (Humańska & Kędziora-Kornatowska, 2009).

Patients after CABG are exposed to secondary obstruction of operated vessels, cardiac disorders, surgical site infection, cardiorespiratory, multi-organ failure, and neurological disorders (stroke, disturbances of consciousness). Cognitive function in terms of non-verbal long-term memory, attention, concentration, psychomotor speed and flexibility may also deteriorate. People qualified for surgery are not only getting older, but they also have more and more co-morbidities, and this affects the occurrence of neuropsychological disorders after the procedure. Operative trauma also leads to a decrease in the immunity, and consequently to nutritional disruptions and an increased risk of the inflammatory process initiation (Biancari et al., 2015).

A previous study found that 58% of patients after cardiac surgery reported loss of appetite in the hospital and complained about disguise possibly induced by anesthesia or mechanical ventilation. Nevertheless, only a few clinical studies have focused on DI after cardiac surgery. It showed that postoperative dietary intake met only 74.4% of their patients' estimated energy requirements at day 5 after cardiac surgeries. Furthermore, decreased DI after surgery has been reported to lead to chronic malnutrition and increased mortality (M. Ogawa et al., 2019).

An important aspect in patients' care after CABG is early diagnosis of mal-nutritional disorders. It helps to properly prepare the patient for surgery and reduces the risk of postoperative complications (Di Gioia et al., 2016).

The aim of this study to assess the nutritional status of patients with ischemic heart disease subjected to coronary artery bypass surgery and physical activity and postoperative complications. Frequently, prior to surgery, malnutrition is unrecognized and untreated. In hospital, the poor nutritional status often deteriorates, thus extending the time of

hospitalization and increasing the risk of complications and death, and longtime fasting before and after surgery also a major cause of nutrition deficiency. Before surgery all parameters should be properly check and if there is any thing seems deficit in the body should be fulfill, anthropometric, biochemical, clinical and dietary assessment should be done before and after surgery. Although biochemical parameters are costly for patients but on the other hand if we see in the next mirror , we bear the prolong stay in hospitals and gets the multiple disease exposure free of cost which can be too much costly even after surgery patients goes in septicemia shock and its increasing the mortality rate. Diet should be properly given to the preoperative and postoperative patients because malnutrition delays the wound healing and prolong stay in hospitals and nursing care setup. Dietary assessment should be done properly for fitness in pre pre- operative and post-operative subjects. It is recommended that medical nutrition therapy should be provided one month before the surgery it will reduce the cost, less chance of infection and will increase the wound healing rapidly.

1.1 Objectives of the study

1. Assessment of nutritional status of pre-operative and post-operative Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting patients.
2. To find out relationship between nutrition and rehabilitation after cardiac surgery.

1.2 Statement of problem

Nutritional support is recognized as a clinically relevant aspect of the intensive care treatment of cardiac surgery patients. Lower albumin levels and unhealthy dietary patterns cause poor nutritional status before surgery lead to increased morbidity and mortality. This poor nutritional status is due to lack of awareness and improper dietary counseling to the majority of population.

1.3 Significance of the study

Poor nutritional status is very common in cardiac surgical patients due to prolong hospital stay and longtime fasting before surgery and delay in start of nutrition therapy after surgery.

Early detection of malnutrition pre-operatively may prevent from many complications and enhance wound healing and prevent from prolong hospital stay post- operatively.

1.4 Study limitations

The sample size in this single-center study was small. Furthermore, only coronary artery bypass grafting diseased patents were taken serum Albumin values were taken as a risk indicator to assess the nutritional status, it was snapshot study, so future studies in longitudinal settings performed for longer periods will be needed to evaluate nutritional intake and the transition of nutritional status. Further research that includes longitudinal assessment of nutrition is needed in the future to investigate whether pre and postoperative nutritional status affects perioperative physical function.

LITERATURE REVIEW

These all studies were based on the role of nutrition in rehabilitation after cardiac surgery. There were also some gaps which were found regarding nutrition therapy and post- operative outcomes.

Cardiovascular disease is a major public health crisis. Mortality rate is increasing day by day, according to 2018 world health organization statistics the cardiovascular disease is top leading mortality rate in non-communicable disease. Taking an estimated 17.9 million live every year (WHO, 2019). In 2013 the cardiovascular disease was 2nd leading cause of mortality worldwide 17 million deaths in world by cardiovascular diseases. More than 80% of these cases in low and middle income countries (Bowry, Lewey, Dugani, & Choudhry, 2015). The global number of deaths from cardiovascular diseases has increased during the past decade by 12.5% (Reddy, 2016). Cardiovascular currently accounts for roughly one third of all deaths in all over the world. These changes are driven by population grown and aging population, with the largest number occurring in countries of south Asia and east Asia due to growing population(Bowry et al., 2015). Cardiovascular death rate is continuously rising in low and middle income countries with rate of up to 300-600 deaths attributed to cardiovascular disease per 100,000 populations

(Alwan, 2011). The death rate of cardiovascular disease in Pakistan is 200,000 deaths annually. Its rising day by day due to lack of physical activity, unbalanced diet, obesity and metabolic disorders. Factors influencing: smoking, family history, history of hypertension or diabetes, obesity, unhealthy diet, lack of physical activity, excessive alcohol intake, deranged values of lipid profile. Cardiovascular diseases death rate can be reduced by modification in modifiable risk factors (Gersh, Sliwa, Mayosi, & Yusuf, 2010). Frequently, before surgery, malnutrition of patients is undiagnosed and untreated, then increases in the hospital prolonging hospitalization, adding to the risk of complications and death and increasing the cost of treatment. Malnutrition deteriorating in the hospital is often a metabolic consequence of the disease, inadequate food intake during the perioperative period as well as the result of perioperative injury. All of these worsen patients' prognosis after leaving the hospital. In surgical patients, it often leads to impairment of cellular and humeral immunity, and among other things, is responsible for the increase in the incidence of infections and difficulties in wound healing process (Ścisło et al., 2014).

A recent study was done in 2018 to 2019 in Japan on 250 patient which were under cardiac surgery .cardiac surgery causes decline in nutritional status due to low dietary intake. Daily DI is measured between 3 and 7 post-operative days. Patients were categorized as DI sufficient or in sufficient or fulfill their requirements or not .functional capacity was also measured as 6MWD (minutes walking distance) pre-operative and at discharge. There is a clear difference is noticed 6MWD post-operatively, it show inadequate nutrition after surgery delays functional recovery, and early nutrition support after surgery support functional recovery (M. Ogawa et al., 2019).

Another study was done in 2018 in Germany on long hospital and ICU stay after surgery which can cause malnutrition in patients and cause poor outcomes. There is evidence that indicates that cardiac surgery patients are more prone to develop malnutrition post-operatively. This may cause infection, poor wound healing,

delayed weaning, and increased the time of stay in ICU and shorter survival time. Early detection of patients who are at risk of malnutrition is also an important step in nutrition therapy. Patients who stay in ICU more than 5 days may develop complications; he may have weakness, prolong mechanical ventilation and sedation time, and gastrointestinal dysfunction. Total 1210 patients were taken in this observational study. This study indicate that patients with prolong ICU stay may experience protein and energy deficits which can cause inflammation, malabsorption metabolic dysfunction and increased loss of nutrients but an early identification of patient at risk may cause adequate nutrition support soon after surgery may prevent further complications (C. Stoppe et al., 2018).

Another research was done in 2018 in Iran. Malnutrition is a major risk factor in cardiac surgery patients and malnutrition has severe consequences in post-operative recovery of the patients. Energy and protein insufficiency are very high in post-surgical patients. In this study 787 patients stay in ICU more than 3 days or at high risk for inadequate nutrition therapy. It was concluded from the study that cardiac nutrition support for patients should be started before surgery. The main goal of nutrition support is to reduce negative protein balance and avoiding starvation and to enhance post-op recovery (Norouzy & Shadnough, 2018).

Another study was done in Germany in 2018 on assessment of nutritional status in pre-operative and post-operative CABG patients .Detecting patients at high nutritional risk is very important for an adequate therapy. Nutritional status assessment scores are rarely used in cardiac surgery patients. Early assessment of pre-operative nutritional status is very important to identify the risk of developing post-operative complications. The role of post-operative nutrition support is to maintain nutritional status and energy requirements in patients during catabolic period after surgery lowers the risk of developing complications and favors shorter stay in hospitals. In cardiac surgery patient's malnutrition is aggravated by long time pre-operative fasting and delay of nutrition support

post-operatively. Nutrition support improves the recovery of patients in many ways, such as; maintenance of metabolism and catabolism, maintenance of gut integrity, reduction of complications after surgery, enhance wound healing and secure proper hydration. Pre-operative time is very important time to optimize nutritional status, correct deficiencies, and enhance immune defense mechanism before surgery. This may lower the risk of developing complications after surgery (Hill, Nesterova, Lomivorotov, Efremov, Goetzenich, Benstoem, Zamyatin, et al., 2018).

The study was done in POLAND in 2016 to 2018. The aim of this study was to assess the nutritional status of patients with ischemic heart disease before and after CABG surgery. Frequently before surgery malnutrition of patients is Undiagnosed. Improper malnutrition is not only characterized by malnutrition, but it also associated with obesity. In hospital with poor nutrition status can cause increase timing of hospitalization, and increase the course of treatment, further it may increase the risk of complications which leads to death. After surgery it may cause impaired immunity which leads to infection and sepsis which accompanied by compromised wound healing. The study was conducted in among 96 hospitalized male patients admit in cardiovascular department of POLAND. The group of people did not receive any nutritional treatment before surgery. Nutritional status is an indicator of proper recovery after surgery. Early identification of abnormal nutritional status may help to reduce complications after surgery, because it is verified that the risk factors that increases morbidity and mortality rates after surgery are associated with pre-operative malnutrition (Ścisło et al., 2019).

An international study was done in 2017, by an international multidisciplinary expert group on nutrition in cardiac surgery. The group of 25 experts from Germany, Canada, Greece, USA and Russia, discussed to identify patients, who have benefit from nutrition support. The patients of cardiac surgery ward are exposed to systemic inflammation causing organ injury and dysfunctions .Which often cause life threatening condition. Patient may loss physical capacity after prolong illness.

Underfeeding is a major problem in cardiac surgery patients. The evidence found in the study that pre-operatively long time fasting causing catabolic stress, insulin resistance and nutrient deficiencies. The study was done on 5400 ventilated patients. The evidence evaluated from study that the surgery associated with malnutrition. This alarming finding is contributed with observations that nutrition support should be start early before surgery (Hill, Nesterova, Lomivorotov, Efremov, Goetzenich, Benstoem, Zamyantin, et al., 2018; Christian Stoppe et al. (2017)).

Another study was done in 2010 in which it was elaborated that nutrition support is an important aspect in cardiac rehabilitation. The others assessed nutrition markers and tested the correlation with inflammatory responses and clinical outcomes of the patients. The plasma concentration was measured of 50 patients in which it was observed from day 0 to day 6, albumin levels increases gradually with inflammatory markers declined. Anemia improved; vitamins turns stable. So, the evidence shows that the standard dietary guidelines followed during rehabilitation after cardiac surgery, enhance recovery (Racca et al. (2010)).

A comparative study upon 200 CABG patients was done in 2015-2016 at Punjab Institute of Cardiology Lahore, Mayo hospital Lahore and Gulab Devi hospital Lahore. In this study outcome after surgery was observed in obese and non-obese patients. According to study excess body fat (obesity) may cause adverse effect on health of the patient which lead to reduce life expectancy and enhance morbidity. Obesity is considered as a risk factor for pre-operative mortality and morbidity with CABG surgery. The patients with high BMI suffer from prolong mechanical ventilation, cause prolong hospital stay, have atrial fibrillation and wound infection. However obesity was not found as an independent predictor of morbidity and mortality after CABG surgery (Akbar, Shah, Ghias, Naseer, & Babur, 2018).

An International study upon poor nutrition status pre -operatively is an important predictor of retardation of rehabilitation after cardiac surgery, was done in 2016 at Japan. Pre-operative physical function and nutrition status are most important predictors of

morbidity and mortality after cardiac surgery. In this study 131 CABG patients were taken and divided in two groups, one with poor nutrition status before surgery, and one with good nutrition status. Different kinds of test were performed on patients after surgery like, hand grip strength test ,6-minute walk test ,muscle strength test, length of stay in ICU ,and length of stay in hospital .It was evaluated that patients with good nutritional status before surgery have better response then the patients with poor nutrition status. Multiple regression analysis revealed that low nutrition status was an independent predictor of retardation of rehabilitation after cardiac surgery (Masato Ogawa et al. (2017).

The study was done at IRAN in 2019, regarding pre-operative poor nutritional status cause delirium in patients after CABG surgery. The aim of the study was to find out association between malnutrition before surgery and occurrence of delirium in patients after CABG surgery. For this study 398 patients were taken pre-operatively, and BMI, mid-upper arm circumference, muscle thickness, Nutrition Risk Screening and subjective global assessment were measured. Delirium was defined as confusion assessment method for the patients of intensive care unit. The evidences prove that postoperative delirium was in 17% of patients. The post-operative delirium was high in those patients who was sever undernourished before surgery. So it was concluded that pre-operative good nutrition status cause good outcomes including good mental condition after cardiac surgery (Velayati, Shariatpanahi, Shahbazi, and Shariatpanahi (2019).

A prospective study was done in Taiwan from 2000 to 2009 to investigate the prevalence of dyslipidemia and hypertension and association with Macro vascular and Micro vascular complication in patients with type II Diabetes Mellitus in Taiwan. According to their study data analysis showed that prevalence of cardiovascular disease was more markedly increased in females who were aged 40 to 60 and >60 years of age than in males with same age group. Strongly linked cardiovascular disease study indicated that females diabetes diagnosed patients had a higher prevalence of myocardial infarction and coronary heart

diseases than diabetic male patients, The prevalence ratios of myocardial infarction were 3.8 for diabetic women and 1.9 for diabetic men. The study further indicated that diabetic women have increased Waist to Hip Ratio and have more adverse lipoprotein change, including greater decreases in High Density Lipoprotein-c, apoA1, and Low-Density Lipoprotein-c size, than do diabetic men. They conclude that they observed progressive increase rate of dyslipidemia, hypertension and deranged values of cholesterol levels plus hypertension (elevated blood pressure) in subjects with diabetes mellitus from 2000 to 2009. Prevalence of diabetic dyslipidemia remained stable in those with micro vascular complications and, indeed, it decreased gradually in patients with macro vascular complications except those with Peripheral Vascular Disease (Khan, Muhammad, & Razaq, 2017).

A cross-sectional study was conducted by doctors at local clinics of Pakistan. The study period was from June 2016 to December 2016. Data was collected from 192 clinics of all over Pakistan, from each community including both rural and urban areas. 9885 participants with age<40 years up to 79 years were recruited. Subjects suffering from high blood pressure, high cholesterol, atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) and having current smoking habit (20 cigarettes per day) and medications especially who were taking antihypertensive therapy were included in the study. Also, both known diabetic subjects and non-diabetes were also included in the study. In their study results mean age of subjects was 49.42 years. Significant difference for basic demographic and clinical characteristics was observed except for diabetes and hypertension. Subjects of age ≥ 50 years had 9 times higher risk of atherosclerosis in atherosclerosis risk score. Subjects with known case of diabetes mellitus 5 times and smokers 2times had greater chance of atherosclerosis. Subjects with high cholesterol and taking treatment for hypertension had greater chance of atherosclerosis. According to their findings were compared with international data which highlighting that history of current smoking, high cholesterol, type 2 diabetes and hypertension are

considered as a major potential underlying risk factors for atherosclerosis in Pakistani individuals (Hassan et al., 2019).

Medical nutrition therapy is an essential component of treatment for dyslipidemia, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases and diabetes mellitus. The focus of nutrition therapy for these conditions includes singular and group instructions to help patients to reduce their lipid profile i.e. total cholesterol, triglycerides level, lipoprotein density level and increase in High density lipoprotein level and to increase fruit vegetables and fiber consumption (Neuhouser, Miller, Kristal, Barnett, & Cheskin, 2012).

These interventions are designed to lower the lipid levels, stabilize blood glucose level, lowering blood pressure and to maintain a healthy weight or to reduce the gained weight.

Substantial evidence shows that these dietary approaches are beneficial for cardiovascular disease prevention (Aaron & Sanders, 2013).

Development of cardiovascular diseases is associated with lifestyle behaviors, such as smoking, unbalanced and unhealthy diet, physical inactivity sedentary behaviors. Physical inactivity is defined as not meeting 150 min weekly performance of moderate physical activity or 75 min of strenuous physical activity. Over three-quarters of deaths due to cardiovascular diseases could be prevented with adequate changes in lifestyle. Indeed, the adoption of healthy life habits such as increasing daily physical activity and decreasing sedentary behaviors can lower the risk of type 2 diabetes, stroke, cardiac related incidence and cardiovascular disease. Improving the quality of life and decreasing risk of death. Several studies have discoursed the importance of increasing physical activity levels as a public health intervention (Alves et al., 2016).

Beneficial effects of physical activity in the prevention of various diseases are widely known and supported by various studies evidence. Different studies have reported protective effect of physical activity on total mortality cardiovascular disease, Diabetes mellitus, hypertension and dyslipidemia in the general population (Franco et al., 2005).

Studies conducted in old aged subjects confirmed that daily physical activity also

reduces significantly mortality risk in elderly people without pre-existent cardiovascular disease (Colecraft, Asante, Christian, & Adu-Afarwuah, 2018).

The relationship between Body Mass Index and Cardiovascular diseases is well documented. Many studies have divided BMI into different distributions of body fat and evidence shows that waist circumference and waist-to-hip ratio is the best predictors of cardiovascular disease (Shields, Tremblay, Connor Gorber, & Janssen, 2012).

Cardiovascular disease is top rank in disease rank in all over the world, according to world health organization every 3rd person is cardiovascular disease patient. In developed countries cardiovascular diseases are decreasing day by day, but in developing countries it is raising rapidly, cardiovascular disease is a multi-factorial disease, unhealthy dietary patterns, Lack of physical activity, higher levels of lipids, Diabetes Mellitus Renal disorders, and liver diseases contributing the progression of cardiovascular disease. If prevention not implemented in coronary artery disease and still unhealthy dietary

patterns, smoking, lack of physical activity it promotes the blockage of coronary arteries. If coronary arteries blocked baldly it appears as myocardial infarction. If angina still persists and blockage increases day by day then there is an option of coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). Coronary artery bypass grafting is very costly in all over the world. Every patient cannot afford the grafting surgery. Even after surgery cases may be more complicated and even co-morbidity can cause death. Medical Nutrition therapy is very effective on each stage of life. If a patient does not smoke, taking healthy diet, doing daily physical activity, managing stress, can reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease and defeat the stage of coronary artery blockage. Awareness should be given in healthy population to reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease. Medical nutrition therapy should be properly provided to cardiovascular disease patients to reduce the risk of progression of cardiovascular disease. Healthy dietary patterns can improve the quality of life and reduce the burden of diseases in all over the world and costly medical surgical

treatment. Balanced diet should be taken because excess fat, carbohydrates and protein cause the storage of excess fat and causing the atherosclerosis in body. Daily physical activity should be done to reduce the progression of cardiovascular disease and atherosclerosis. Improper nutrition can cause the delay in surgery healing wound. Balanced diet can improve the quality of life after surgery.

3.1 Methodology

This was hospital based descriptive study. This study was conducted in Rawalpindi institute of cardiology, department of intensive care unit and cardiac surgery ward within 3 months from February 2025 to April 2025. Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used with sample size of 65 CABG patients who fulfill the inclusion criteria. Consent was taken from

patients and confidentiality of patients maintained.

3.2 Study design

It was hospital based descriptive study.

3.3 Study population

There were Total 65 patients 46 were male and 19 females taken for the study who were admitted for CABG Surgery in Rawalpindi Institute of Cardiology.

3.4 Study locality and duration of study

The data was collected from Indoor patients of intensive care unit and cardiac surgery ward at Rawalpindi institute of cardiology (RIC) tertiary care hospital, a 300 bedded hospital which is located on Rawal Road near Noor khan Air base Rawalpindi.

3.5 Sample size

65 patients both gender male and female patients were included in study who undergoing CABG surgery enrolled for the study.

3.6 Inclusion criteria

Only admitted patients were the part of study Age >30
adult patients
All patients of coronary heart disease All
patients of CABG
Patient undergoing on-pump surgery

3.6.1 Exclusion criteria

Age <30

Other than CABG diseased patients were excluded Unwilling patients were excluded from study Impaired cognitive Patient undergoing other cardiac procedures Patients with Co-Morbid

3.7 Sampling Technique

It was non-probability consecutive sampling technique in which all accessible subjects were the part of the sample. This sample technique was considered as a best non- probability

sampling technique because it includes all available subjects to make the sample a better representation of the entire population.

3.8 Data Collection Tools

In addition to above noted tools, following research tools were also included.

- a) Sphygmomanometer (Blood Pressure measuring Apparatus)
- b) Weighing machine with stadiometer (scale)
- c) Stethoscope
- d) Calculator
- e) Computer

3.8.1 Demographic Data

Demographic data was obtained from patients by taking history through interviewing the patients and through hospital records by history sheets.

Anthropometric Assessment

Height, weight and body mass index(kg/m²) were taken according to Asians by weighing machine and measuring rod .The BMI was classified into five categories which are Underweight <18.5, Normal weight (18.5-22.9), Overweight (23-24.9), Obesity (>25kg/m²)

Biochemical Assessment

Serum Albumin levels, Hemoglobin levels, and Blood Glucose levels were taken for Biochemical assessment.

Albumin: Albumin is high quality protein made by liver. Albumin helps keep fluid in blood stream, so it does not leak into other tissues. It is also a carrier of different substances in throughout the body including hormones, vitamins, and enzymes. Low albumin levels are also a sign of malnutrition. For analyze serum Albumin level in the blood, blood sample was collected and stored in a tube containing anticoagulant and send to laboratory where through AU480 Beckman Coulter analyzer sample analyzed, test performed, and printed results were automatically performed. Reference range for albumin is 3.5-5.0 g/dl (34-50g/l).

Hemoglobin: Hemoglobin is a protein in red blood cells that carries oxygen from lung to the body. Low hemoglobin levels in blood are a sign of blood disorder and it shows that patient taking diet which is low in iron and minerals. Sample taken from vein and stored it into an anticoagulant having container and send to laboratory. Where Celldyn Ruby of Aborts analyzer was used and printed results were generated. Normal range of Hemoglobin is 12-15 g/dl.

Blood glucose levels:

Blood glucose levels were checked through glucometer present in every department of RIC hospital that is EASYGLUCO ultra plus and through taking sample by vein and send to the laboratory. Printed results generated.

Clinical Examination

Clinical assessment of CABG patients

- Chest pain
- Faigue
- Palpitation

- Arrhythmias
- Swelling in hands and feet

3.8.2 Dietary Assessment

Dietary assessment was done with the help of food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) and 24 hour recall method was used for both pre-operatively and post-operatively at day 3rd after surgery. FFQ which are most commonly used method of measuring diet in dietary habits. The food items were taken from 05 food groups which were high in carbohydrates, protein, Fat and oil. Most of the food items having high content of saturated fat (animal fat) diet i.e. Desi ghee , full cream milk, butter, ice cream, egg yolk, high salty diet, alcohol, cigarette smoking were also included in the questionnaire.

3.9 Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was done by using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version. Descriptive statistics were presented as mean,

median, mode, frequencies and standard deviation. Pearson’s correlation test was performed to find out relationship between dependent and independent variables. Paired T-test was performed upon albumin levels and prolongs hospital stay. Dietary assessment was done through Nutri Survey software.

3.10 Ethical Consideration

This study was conducted after taking written approval from the concerned head of the department of In Door Patients and from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of RIC Rawalpindi. Subjects were briefed about the study objectives and their satisfaction was obtained. Approval was taken from every participant through consent form Results and discussions

A total of 65 patients of coronary artery bypass graft surgery were included in this study. There were 46 (68.7%) male and 19 (28.4%) female.

Figure 4.1 Gender distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the frequency distribution of gender. It was observed that from 65 participants, there were 19 (28%) female patients and 46 (68%) male patients. This distribution shows that the ratio of cardiac diseases is higher in males than females.

Figure 4.2 Age group of patients

Age group ranging from 30 to 70 years, Age group was divided in two categories, 30 to 50 years and 51 to 70 years. The minimum age was 35 years and maximum age was 70 years figure

4.2 shows that in 30-50 years of age group the patients were 28(44%) and in 51-70 years age group 37(56%).

Figure 4.3 Living home town of patients

Figure 4.3 shows that 38.4 % patients were from rural areas and 61.5% patients were from Urban. It was found that the patients who were living in urban areas were more prone to cardiac illness than rural areas patients.

Figure 4.4 Monthly Incomes of participants

Descriptive statistics was applied upon the income of the participants and divided into four groups. Figure 4.4 shows that the Maximum Number of patients lying in middle class with pay 25000-40000 was higher in number in study. The minimum number of patients were in >60000 monthly income 4(6%) patients.

Figure 4.5 Nutritional status of subjects

BMI was assessed of 65 patients by taking weight in kg and height in cm.

Figure 4.5 shows that 1(1.53%) were underweight, In Normal Body mass index category 21(32%) had Normal BMI, 36(55%) subjects were overweight and 7 (10.70%) were Obese. The minimum BMI was 17.60 kg/m² and Maximum BMI was 40 kg/ m². The Mean BMI was 26.18 with 4.1± SD. It was found that most of the participants were overweight.

Figure 4.6 Physical activities of Patients

Figure 4.6 shows that 51(76.1%) were doing daily walk, 7(10.4%) were jogging daily, 4(6%) were doing stair climbing exercise and 3(4.5%) were doing treadmill exercise.

Figure 4.7 Risk factors/ drivers

Figure 4.7 shows that in clinical history of the patients 55% had hypertension, 30.70% had diabetes mellitus type 1 and type 2. 61.50% were still smoking which may progression of cardiovascular disease and myocardial attack, 46.10% patients were overweight which is also indicating the progression of cardiovascular disease. The risk factors were higher in male patients as compared to the female patients.

Table 4.1 Pre and post-operative nutrition predictions

Variables	Mean	SD	Range
Weight	71.04	11.53	50-99.5
Height	165.1	8.52	132-182
Albumin (pre-op)	3.17	0.57	2.1-4.0
Albumin (post-op)	2.97	0.53	2.0-3.8
Hemoglobin (pre-operative)	13.96	1.45	11.4-16.8
Hemoglobin (post-operative)	11.6	1.64	7.90-14.90
BMI	26.1	4.1	17.60-40.80

This table shows means, standard deviation and minimum level to maximum level and albumin levels (pre and post-operative) of the nutritional predictors that depict nutritional status CABG surgery patients. Pre-operative status was based on BMI kg/m², Hemoglobin levels pre-operative,

and Albumin levels pre-operative. Post-operative nutritional status was based on post-operative Albumin levels and post-operative Hemoglobin level.

Figure 4.8 Electrolytes levels of patients

Figure 4.8 shows Electrolytes levels of patients, 69% patients had balanced serum sodium levels while 30.7% patients had Hypernatremia.

Table 4.2 length of stay in hospital

Total	Mean	St. Deviation	Range	Min	Max
65	7.4769	2.33926	11.00	5.00	16.00

This table 4.2 shows the length of stay in hospital. The Mean days hospital stay was 7.47 with SD 2.33±. The minimum hospital days were 5 days and maximum stay was 16 days with pre and post-operative surgery.

Figure 4.9 Hemoglobin levels of patients

This figure shows that normal Hb levels were 90.7% pre-operatively and 47.6% post operatively, and low Hb levels pre-operatively were 9.2% and 52.30% post-operatively. This shows most of the patients have normal Hb levels pre-operatively.

Figure 4.10 Pre and post-operative Albumin levels of patients

Pre-operative and post operation serum Albumin levels were taken from subjects. Figure 4.10 shows frequency distribution of serum albumin. 41.50% patients had normal serum albumin levels while 58.40 patients were in hypoalbuminemia stage, on the other hand in post-operative biochemical serum albumin levels 32.30% patient had normal values while 67.60% patients had deranged serum albumin levels

Figure 4.11 Clinical Picture of subjects

Figure 4.11 shows that 40% patients had mild to moderate on and off chest pain, 22.20% had fatigue, 22.20% were recorded in arrhythmia stages and 15.50% subjects had swelling on limbs

with mild to moderate Edema. Most of the patients were taking medicines for all above symptoms.

Table 4.3 Association of Serum Albumin level Pre and post-operative hospital stay

Nutritional Predictor	Stay in hospital	Stay in hospital	P-Value
Albumin	5-6 days	>6 days	
Normal	26 (40%)	-	0.000
Hypo-albuminemia	3 (4.6%)	36 (55.3%)	

Table 4.3 shows statistically significant association between serum Albumin levels, a nutritional predictor and recovery after surgery or stay in hospital after Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting. This indicate that patient with normal albumin levels had satisfactory recovery after surgery. On the other hand, patient with low albumin levels had more stay in hospital with enhance recovery timings.

Table 4.4 Association of Body Mass Index pre and post operative hospital stay

Nutritional Predictor	Stay in hospital		P-Value
	5-6 days	>6 days	
BMI(kg/m ²)	5-6 days	>6 days	
Normal Weight	25(38.4%)	1(1.5%)	0.000
Overweight	-	39(60%)	

Table 4.4 shows significance relationship between BMI and stay in hospital after cardiac surgery. Patient with overweight and with high BMI takes more time for recovery and wound healing and

they stay in hospital more days then the patients with normal BMI.

Table 4.5 Association of Hemoglobin level pre and post operative

Nutritional Predictor	Stay in hospital		P-Value
	5-6 days	>6 days	
Hemoglobin	5-6 days	>6 days	
Normal	24(36.9%)	36 (55.3%)	0.648
Anemia	4(6.1%)	1 (1.5%)	

Table 4.5 shows no significant relationship between pre-operative hemoglobin levels and stay in hospital after CABG surgery. This indicates 60

patients have normal Hemoglobin levels and there was no any major finding which shows association between hemoglobin and hospital stay.

Table 4.6 Comparison of preoperative and post operative 24 hour caloric intake

Nutrients	Mean	Range	DRI(mean)	P-value
Energy(Kcal/day) Pre-operative Post-operative	±2291.1 ±2006.6	1186-3650 1240-2765	(Made by Food and Nutrition Board of the Institution of Medicine)±2227	0.033 0.33

Pre-operative and post-operative 24 hour calories assessment was done through 24 hours dietary recall from every patient, and compare their means with recommended dietary intake, it was found that mostly before and after surgery calories consumption by patients does not met DRIs during their hospital stay, especially post-operatively due to long

time anesthesia patient complaint for Anorexia, and there is no started proper nutritional therapy after surgery by health care provider can also

cause low nutritional status or malnutrition. Which with other factors cause poor outcomes or delay in rehabilitation after surgery.

Figure 4.11 food frequency data

Food frequency data was taken through food frequency questionnaire; it was analyzed by Nutri-survey software. The Analysis data shows that energy intake was decreasing day by day, Protein intake was 84%, fat intake was 61%, and Carbohydrates intake was 58%. Dietary fiber was 80% which is very good for cardiovascular disease patients. Polyunsaturated fatty acids intake was 57%, Vitamin A intake was higher than recommended Allowance. In average patients were taking 98% sodium as recommended, potassium intake was lower which is 63%, calcium intake was 39%, magnesium was 76%, phosphorus was 136% which is slightly higher than recommendations. Iron intake was 80% and zinc intake was 130%.

4.1 Discussion

Cardiovascular disease is the top leading cause of death globally. The epidemiological data is showing relationship between various diseases states, especially cardiovascular disease, unhealthy dietary patterns, like low intake of dietary fiber

and antioxidants, high intake of saturated fat and refined sugar(Diehr & Beresford, 2003).

The present study was carried out to assess nutritional status of pre-operative and post-operative Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting patients and to find the relationship between nutrition and rehabilitation after cardiac surgery. In this study 21(32.3%) subjects had normal BMI, In overweight category the total subjects were 36(55.3%), In obese category the total obese subjects were 7(10.7%). In this study mostly subjects were overweight which is considered as the major risk factors of progression of cardiovascular disease and increasing the mortality rate, other studies results also shows that obesity plays an important role in increasing risk of cardiovascular disease, Myocardial infarction, Atherosclerosis and diabetes mellitus. Similar study was done in 2015 in British population to check the prevalence of obesity and the prevailing risk factors of cardiovascular disease, studied data showed that obese subjects

had higher risk developing of cardiovascular disease, Myocardial infarction(Owen et al., 2015). Nutritional status is an indicator conditioning proper recovery of the patient after the surgery. Early identification of the abnormal state of nutrition and the implemented measures reduce the risk of post-operative complications resulting from malnutrition or excessive body weight. Caring for the geriatric patient after an operation should combine not only the risk associated with the surgical trauma, but also changes characteristic of the patient's age. Consequences resulting from the aging process contribute to the occurrence of biological, mental, and social disorders. As a result, elderly people are more at risk of complications after surgery, including complications resulting from abnormal nutritional status (Skokowska & Dyk, 2010). Morbidity and mortality rate are increasing due to high blood pressure day by day in all over the world. Epidemiologic data indicate a continuous incremental risk of cardiovascular disease in relation to the blood pressure(Kannel, Vasan, & Levy, 2003). Smoking has been associated with a two to four fold increased risk of coronary heart disease, a 70% excess mortality from cardiovascular disease and sudden cardiac arrest (Lakier, 1992). It is estimated that 1 in 10 deaths in all over the world are caused by smoking. It is also estimated that the death rate of tobacco smoking will raise up to 8.3 million in 2030 (Yang & Dong, 2019). In this study smoking habits, 25(37.3%) subjects were non nonsmokers, 26(20.9%) subjects were Ex-smoker, while 26(38%) subjects were currently smoking. The current smokers were from 30-50 years age group. The global prevalence of smoking in men is 25%. half of whom live in 3 Asian countries India, China, Indonesia, it is also noted that numbers increased in young male and females in Asia region (Dong et al., 2011). It is noted that smoking in cardiovascular disease increasing the 30% more chance of myocardial infarction and sudden cardiopulmonary death (Ambrose & Barua, 2004). Smoking cessation is beneficial in cardiovascular disease; even in old age it decreases the risk factors of cardiovascular disease, Myocardial infarction and stroke and sudden cardiac arrest (Mons et al., 2015). After >15 years of smoking cessation, the risk of cardiac failure and death for most Ex- smokers becomes

similar to that subjects who never smoke (Ahmed et al., 2015).

Physical activity reduces the risk factors of cardiovascular disease. Various studies suggest that minimum 30 minutes moderate intensity physical activity including brisk walk, reduces the incidence of cardiovascular disease in male and female subjects. Regular exercise may also delay the progression in cardiovascular disease (Bassuk & Manson, 2003). In this study 51(76%) were doing daily brisk walk. 7(10.4%) were jogging 2-3 times in a week, 4(6%) were doing stair climbing exercise. 3(4.5%) were doing treadmill exercise.

In co-morbidity >45 years of age subjects had multiple disease like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, Renal disorders and multi stages of coronary artery disease.

In hospital stay data 22(38%) patients recovered in five days. 12(18%) patients recovered in seven days, these patients were above 60 years of age and had good nutritional status before and after surgery. Other patients had prolonged stay data like 3(5%) patients stay for 16 days because of their low albumin level, deranged other biochemical values and low nutritional status .Other studies data also shows that total reserve capacity is reduced in the elderly, increases in the prolonged use of ventilation and in prolonged hospital stays after operation and the decrease in postoperative physical function have become annoying problems (Bridges, Edwards, Peterson, Coombs, & Ferguson, 2003). Another study shows that Postoperative CABG length of stay is longer with increasing age: 8 days

for <80 years of age, 10.89 days for 80–84 years of age, and 11.54 days for >85 years of age (Likosky et al., 2009).

Lower levels of serum albumin were associated with a higher incidence of postoperative complications and greater lengths of stay. The highest prevalence of complications recorded in those patients with serum albumin levels less than 2.5 g/dL. There was no association between preoperative serum albumin levels and saphenous vein harvest site infections. Many Studies also elaborates that low levels of serum albumin may prolong hospital stay, late recovery of wounds and other complications with such patients (Fanali et al., 2017).

In dietary patterns dietary salt intake data was taken according to the results 45(67%) patients were taking some time. 14(21%) were taking often, 6(9%) were never added the salt in their dietary intake in daily routine. The less intake of dietary salt can reduce the risk and progression of cardiovascular disease, various countries guidelines recommends that less intake of dietary salt should be practice. Higher intake of salt can cause Hyponatremia, Hypertension, cardiovascular diseases and renal disorders. Reduction of dietary salt can prevent the cardiovascular diseases and reversal of coronary artery disease (Adler et al., 2014). A study was done in 2011 in normotensive and hypertensive patients to check the association of salt intake and cardiovascular disease, according to their results salt reduction was associated with reductions in sodium excretion of between 27 and 39 mmol/24 hour and reduction in systolic blood pressure 1 and 4mmhg. Hypertensive subjects found less progression of cardiovascular disease as compared to who were taking frequently salt (Taylor, Ashton, Moxham, Hooper, & Ebrahim, 2011).

In dietary intake pre-operative 24-hour intake the Mean intake was 2291 \pm 491 calories, the minimum intake was 1186 calories and maximum caloric intake was 3650 calories.

Post-operative Mean intake was 2006 \pm 358, Minimum Intake was 1240 calories Maximum was 2760 calories. It was observed that pre-operative few patients were taking below or near to BMR and few were taking above the recommended intake .A decreased dietary intake can lead to weight loss and resultant

malnutrition. During hospitalization, dietary intake is less than adequate in older adults. Plate waste, defined as food attempted to be eaten by the patient but incompletely consumed, was found to be 30% in one Swedish hospital and as high as 41% on geriatric units(DiMaria-Ghalili, 2018). A counseling session was done with such patients to balance their diet for to reduce the complications after surgery, counseling was done very effectively. It was observed that in post-operative 24 hours recall data the minimum intake was improved by patients but due to post anesthesia complications they took up to BMR which was 1240 calories per day and maximum intake which few patients were taking above the recommended intake also observed balanced which was 2765 calories according to their body composition.

Food frequency data shows that all subject's energy intake was 63%, protein intake was 84%, fat intake was 61%, carbohydrates intake was 58%, dietary fiber intake was 84%, polyunsaturated fatty acids intake was 57%. Vitamin A intake was higher than recommended daily intake. Sodium intake was 98%, Potassium intake was 63%, calcium intake was 39%, magnesium intake was 76%, iron intake was 80% and zinc intake was 130%, it was observed that the fruit intake not met according to daily recommended allowance.

A study done in 2008 by DiMaria-Ghalili systematically examined the relationship between nutrition markers (BMI, serum albumin, and transferrin levels) before surgery and again at 4–5 days post-surgery and 4–6 weeks post discharge, as well as biomedical and general health outcomes, in 91 elderly patients undergoing elective CABG surgery. Although older patients undergoing elective CABG had a normal preoperative nutrition status, weight loss during the later phases of the surgical stress response was problematic. Older patients undergoing elective CABG lost an average of 5.2% \pm 4.3% of their weight from pre surgery to 6 weeks post discharge. The more weight lost during this period, the lower their level of self-reported physical health and the greater their chances of being readmitted to the hospital. Thus, older CABG patients who lose weight in the postoperative period may increase their vulnerability to adverse health outcomes, including hospital readmission.

Summary

A hospital based descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi institute of cardiology Rawal road Rawalpindi to assess the Assessment of nutritional status of pre-operative and post-operative Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting patients and to find out relationship between nutrition and rehabilitation after cardiac surgery.

The admitted patients of the hospital were included in the study. These patients were already known case of cardiovascular disease and admitted for coronary Artery Bypass Grafting.

The study sample comprise of 65 subjects 46(30%) male and 19(30%) females 30-70 years age group from rural and urban area with demographic characteristics including age in years, education level, occupation and monthly income.

In smoking habits, 25(37.3%) subjects were nonsmokers, 26(20.9%) subjects were Ex-smoker, while 26(38%) subjects were currently smoking. The current smokers were from 30-50 years age group.

In physical activity 51(76%) were doing daily brisk walk. 7(10.4%) were jogging 2-3 times in a week, 4(6%) were doing stair climbing exercise. 3(4.5%) were doing treadmill exercise.

In co-morbidity >45 years of age subjects had multiple disease like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, Renal disorders and multi stages of coronary artery disease.

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Lower levels of serum albumin were associated with a higher incidence of postoperative complications and greater lengths of stay. The highest prevalence of complications recorded in those patients with serum albumin levels less than 2.5 g/dl. There was no association between preoperative serum albumin levels and saphenous vein harvest site infections.

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Conclusion

Poor nutritional status, hypoalbuminemia and BMI >25 found delay in wound healing, prolong hospitalization, other complications. Post-operative patients had more poor nutritional status than preoperative patients.

Recommendations

Specific Recommendations

Recent and older studies support a primary role for modification in diet and certain lifestyle changes to reduce the progression of cardiovascular disease, hypertension, Diabetes mellitus, obesity and metabolic syndromes. In the light of findings and conclusion of present study, the following recommendations are for coronary artery bypass grafting patients.

Obesity is risk factor for coronary artery bypass grafting, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes mellitus, weight gain is the greater risk of myocardial infarction, stroke and renal failure. Reduction of weight is the key to reduce the risk factors from above diseases. It is recommended that BMI of subjects should be within normal range or slightly below normal range. Now a day job is the very stressful part of life, stress increases the body weight, and raises the blood pressure among subjects, so 6 monthly or annually a proper medical examination should be done with baseline investigations including ECG, Echocardiography. Their job should be short duration and stress free.

The sedentary lifestyle increasing the progression of cardiovascular disease, hypertension and diabetes mellitus, it is recommended that regular physical activity should be encouraged to control the blood pressure, less resistance of insulin and to burn the body fat, efforts should be made to encourage the stop smoking.

Animal saturated fat like high fat meat, organs like brain, kidney, liver, paye, increases the lipid profile in subjects, resulting the hypertension, cardiovascular disease, ischemic heart disease and atherosclerosis. It is recommended that subjects should restrict the intake of high fat meat specially organs meat.

Low levels of serum albumin can cause delay wound healing, prolong hospital stay and other complications in pre-operative and post-operative subjects, a fruitful diet should be added in their diet, and seasonal fruits should be added.

Patient with sedentary lifestyle should be mild to moderate active before and after surgery, 75 minutes of exercise per week should be done. Patient with asthmatic attack and angina should avoid physical activity.

General Recommendations

It is also recommended that processed food, samosa, pakora, fried chips, burger, should be consumed in moderation, bakery items, biscuits, soft drinks, cold drinks, chips, should be avoided because these items are high in salt and sugar which increases the risk factors of CVD, DM, HTN and MI.

It is recommended that chicken egg should be consumed in moderation; whole egg should be consumed 2 times in a day. If lipid profile deranged only egg white should be taken instead whole egg, because a whole egg contains 213 mg cholesterol.

Various dietary guidelines recommend the saturated fat should be consumed < 10% of daily caloric intake. High intake of saturated fat increases the lipid levels in the body, resulting the atherosclerosis and progression in disease. The consumption of unsaturated fat and polyunsaturated fatty acids should be consumed more.

Fish and chicken are low in fat and low in cholesterol, it is recommended that white meat i.e. fish and chicken should be taken instead of red meat beef or mutton. Fish should be consumed once weekly, because fish is the good source of omega-3 fatty acids and omega-6 fatty acids.

It is recommended that fresh fruits and green leafy vegetables should be consumed frequently, because fruits and vegetables are the good source of dietary fiber, vitamins, minerals and phytochemicals. Fresh fruits and vegetable are also good source of potassium and low in sodium, potassium is essential for cardiac muscles and to maintain the blood pressure.

DASH (dietary approaches to stop hypertension) diet should be taken in routine diet, DASH diet is the low in sodium, high in potassium, and plenty of fruits and vegetables. Salt intake should not be consumed more than 2grams, if the disease is progressing salt restriction should be strictly monitoring, should not be more than 1 gm per day in diet. Blood pressure should be controlled to prevent the kidney disease.

The general public requires preventive advice related health behavior. The whole community must be mobilized and made aware of the possibility of prevention of hypertension, cardiovascular disease and other chronic diseases.

In developing countries like Pakistan in all communities after age 35 the all baseline investigation including ECG, ECHO should be done after every 6 months or annually free of cost to diagnose the cardiovascular disease in early age. Blood pressure should be monitor properly to diagnose the essential hypertension.

Social media, print media and Electronic media can play a vital role to create awareness regarding prevention of cardiovascular disease and other chronic diseases.

Authors Contribution

RS collection of data

FM conceived, designed, and did statistical analysis of manuscript

ED manuscript writing

AM collection of data

BR manuscript writing

AA did review and final approval of manuscript (Mentor)

MS did review and final approval of manuscript (Mentor)

FDK manuscript writing

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Appendices
Annex i

ASSESSMENT OF NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF PRE& AND POST-OPERATIVE CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING (CABG) SURGERY PATIENTS

Anthropometric and demographic datas

PATIENT Name: _____ Age: _____ yrs Gender: Male
Female

Weight in Kg: _____ Height in cm: _____

Dibestes: YES NO HTN: YES NO

Living area/Residence a. Urban b. rural

Job/Way of income a. Government servant b. Private job c. Retired d. House wife

Monthly Income .15000-25000 b. 25000-4000 c. 40000-6000 d. >60000

Using added salt in diet a. sometime b. Often c. Never

Cigarette smoking .Current Smoker b. smoke per day _____ c. Nonsmoker d. Ex-smoker

Use of drinks a. Alcohol b. wine c. Beer d. coke/Pepsi

Physical activity a. Light b. Moderate c. Heavy

Type of exercise a. Walking <30 min 30 min >30 min

b. Jogging c. Stair climbing d. Treadmill

BMI a. Normal b. Overweight c. Obese

Changes in BMI in last six months

a. Marked changes b. Mild changes c. No changes

Biochemical and clinical data

Labs investigations	Test performed	Results pre-op	Results post-op
Hemoglobin			
Albumin levels pre- operatively			
Albumin level post operatively			

Variables

ANTHROPOMETRIC	BIOCHEMICAL	RISK FACTORS	DEMOGRAPHIC
WEIGHT	HB LEVELS PRE- OPERATIVE	DIABETES MELLITUS	AGE
HEIGHT	ALBUMIN POST- OPERATIVE	HYPERTENTION	GENDER
BMI	HB LEVELS POST- OPERATIVE	SMOKING	INCOME
		ADDED SALT INTAKE	

Clinical assessment of CABG patients

1. Chest pain	yes	no
2. Fatigue	yes	no
4. Arrhythmias	yes	no
5. Swelling in hands and feet	yes	no

Annex ii

FOOD FREQUENCY QUESTIONNAIRE

Carbohydrates

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-2 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Bread	One slice					
Whole bread chapatti	One					
Rice	One cup					
Potatoes	One					
Pasta	One cup					
Biscuit	One					

Meat and proteins

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Beef						
Chicken						

Fish						
Eggs						
Liver ,brains, kidneys						
Lentils						

Dairy foods and fats

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Whole milk						
Yogurt						
Ice cream						
Cheese						
Margarine						
Butter						

Fruits

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Apple						
Grapes						
Grapefruit						
Pomegranate						
Dates						
Banana						

Vegetables

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Cabbage						
Carrots						
Spinach						
Tomatoes						
Chick peas						
Fresh beans						

Beverges

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Tea						
Coffee						
Pepsi/coke						
Beer						
Red wine						
Carbonated fruit drinks						

Fast foods and bakery products

Food	Amount	Never/1In month	1-3 per month	1 per week	2-4 per week	Daily
Pizza						
Burger						
Rools						
Cakes						
Pasteries						
Fried sandwiches						

College and universities with years attended and degrees obtained Memberships in
learned or honorary societies

BS Nursing from Punjab University Lahore, General Nursing from Allied Hospital Faisalabad.

Publications

nil

Date__

